

D6.7

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED

Exploitation and Sustainability Plan - initial

WHITE

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ABBREVIATIONS

CA	Consortium Agreement
BG	Background
CIRCE	Centro de Investigación de Recursos y Consumos Energéticos
CU	Control Union Certifications Germany GmbH
EC	European Commission
ECOS	Environmental Coalition on Standards
EM	Exploitation Manager
EU	European Union
FG	Foreground
GA	Grant Agreement
IP	Intellectual property
IPR	Intellectual property rights
PAB	Project Advisory Board
PC	Project Coordinator
PMQP	Project Management and Quality Plan
SC	Steering Committee
TBD	To be defined
WEcR	Wageningen Economic Research
WFBR	Wageningen Food and Biobased Research
WHITE	White Research SPRL
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader
WR	Wageningen Research

Executive Summary

Sound Innovation and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) management is critical in order to enable the successful exploitation and market deployment of the wide range of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED assets. Therefore, the consortium of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED places a great emphasis on managing exploitation and IPR in the framework of the project, with a view to effectively pave the way for the smooth exploitation and the reassurance of sustainability of its results after its completion.

Along these lines, the current report presents the **initial version of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Exploitation and Sustainability Plan**. In particular, this deliverable defines the IPR work performed within WP6 - Dissemination, exploitation and communication. It sheds light on the key terms pertaining to the management and protection of intellectual property and lays down the main components of the relevant methodology to be applied throughout the project.

The report provides a preliminary description of the project results, along with initial identification of the contributing partners as well as protection types and access rights. Additionally, it presents an overview of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's assets as envisioned at this stage of the project and the initial considerations of background and foreground IP, as currently perceived by the project partners. The methodology applied is supported by the IPR Matrix that facilitates registration of all background and foreground IPR and helps the timely identification and resolution of any potential conflict in this respect.

The report will be further elaborated and updated if needed on a regular basis as the project progresses. The final version of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Exploitation and Sustainability Plan will be delivered by the end of the project, to guide post-project exploitation of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's results.

1. Introduction

The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED partners focus on producing results that will be sustained after the project's completion and ensuring that innovative ideas, methodologies, and results of the project will be fully identified, preserved and considered in terms of commercialisation potential. Thus, the consortium defines basic principles, from the early stages of the project, that will yield a solid management framework for the Background (BG), as well as the Foreground (FG) Intellectual Property Rights of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED. The project's **SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Exploitation and Sustainability Plan** sets the ground for monitoring the protection of IPs and IPR within and outside the consortium, which eventually will support the creation of value regarding the exploitable assets of the project and will facilitate a successful innovation.

The current report presents the **initial version** of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Exploitation and Sustainability Plan that aims to identify the project's key assets, set the premises for the determination of their underlying IPR and the development of a common understanding regarding their exploitation framework after the completion of the project.

The initial version of the Exploitation and Sustainability Plan is comprised of 5 distinct chapters, as follows:

- **Chapter 1** provides introductory information about the context in which this report has been elaborated as well as its targets and structure.
- **Chapter 2** clarifies the key terms pertaining to IPR management of the project, defines the underlying objectives and explains the main intellectual property protection instruments to be employed.
- **Chapter 3** outlines the IPR management strategy and its underlying stages in the context of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED and describes the methodology to be followed in this respect.
- **Chapter 4** introduces the IPR Matrix and explains the procedures followed in order to identify the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED background and foreground IPs, as perceived at this stage of the project.
- **Chapter 5** offers a preliminary overview of the project's assets to be co-created, as identified at this stage of the project, as well as the background and foreground IPs as perceived by all SUSTCERT4BIOBASED partners.
- **Chapter 6** concludes on the next steps towards the exploitation of the assets of the project.

The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Exploitation and Sustainability Plan will be updated and further elaborated on a systematic basis throughout the project. Specifically, a finalised, updated version is expected at the end of the project (M36) and will include the description of the final project's assets as well as the consortium's plans regarding their IPR protection and their main exploitation routes which will facilitate their exploitation after the end of the project.

2. IPR Management overview

2.1 Objectives

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED IPR management objectives reflect the need to protect project assets with a view of ensuring the commercial rollout of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's exploitable results along with their proper dissemination. To this end, the objectives of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's Exploitation and Sustainability Plan are the following:

- Describe the IPR management methodology to be followed during the lifetime of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED.
- Identify the assets that will emerge from foreseen activities within the lifecycle of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED thus, determining an assets' portfolio from the early stages of the project.
- Develop a common understanding among the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED partners, concerning terms and issues of the BG and FG IPs and respective access rights.
- Conceptualise a preliminary frame of the IP protection that will be employed in each identified exploitable asset of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED.
- Define and eventually dissolve any possible IP conflicts within the consortium and beyond.
- Establish common guidelines and actions within the consortium to safeguard the smooth operation of the IPR strategies to be implemented.

The key concepts to consider for designing the Exploitation and sustainability Plan are the following:

- Background IP
- Foreground IP
- Exploitable results
- Access rights
- IP protection

The following sub-chapters present the definitions of these concepts.

2.2 Definitions

2.2.1 *Background IP*

Background IP can be **defined as data, know-how or information – including any rights - owned or licensed to a project partner prior to the commencement of the agreement and needed to implement the action or exploit the project's assets**¹. The background needed for carrying out the project activities or exploiting the underlying results must be accessible to the other project partners **on a royalty-free basis**. Under this frame, all project partners must identify the background

¹ See Article 16 of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Grant Agreement, p.32

as pertinent for the project actions and grant access rights to this IP². The background of a project can be identified and agreed:

- (i) within the consortium agreement, after the internal evaluation of pre-existing knowledge, or
- (ii) in a separate agreement (“agreement on the background”).

In this respect, there are two main aspects to consider when dealing with the background of a project³ :

- **Identification of background:** Naming of the assets that each project partner provides to the consortium and which are imperative for the successful implementation and exploitation of the project actions.
- **Definition of Access Rights:** Clarification of the rights to use knowledge under the terms and conditions agreed within the consortium and align with the underlying background rules and obligations set by the EC in order to ensure the smooth implementation of the project.

2.2.2 Foreground IP

Foreground refers to **the results and assets that are generated through the implementation of project activities**, including pieces of information, materials, and knowledge⁴. These results comprise any tangible or intangible output of the project’s actions which can be protectable or not. In this respect, foreground IP can arise and be obtained from project partners in order to protect and exploit the underlying exploitable results of the project. It includes intellectual property rights (e.g. copyrights, industrial designs, patents), similar forms of protection (e.g. rights for databases) and unprotected know-how (e.g. confidential material). It should be noted that results generated outside the project activities cannot be defined as foreground.

The Grant Agreement of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED establishes that results of the project are owned by the project partner who generates them⁵. Given the collaborative nature of the project, some results can be jointly developed by several partners. In this case, **joint ownership can arise among the contributing partners and is subject to the agreement on the allocation and terms of the exercise of their joint ownership**. Although regulations concerning the frame of joint ownership are embedded in the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Grant Agreement⁶, it would be best practice for partners to establish during the project implementation a separate joint ownership agreement in order to define the allocation and terms of exercising their ownership. Each joint owner can grant non-exclusive licenses to third parties to exploit the joint-owned results unless otherwise agreed in the CA or the joint ownership agreement.

² See Attachment 1 in the Consortium Agreement for a detailed description of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED background and the access rights granted.

³ European Commission, European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency, Scherer, J., Weber, S., Alveen, P., et al., *European IP Helpdesk : successful valorisation of knowledge and research results in Horizon Europe : boosting the impact of your project through effective communication, dissemination and exploitation*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2022, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2826/437645>

⁴ For a detailed definition of the Foreground see: <https://iprhelpdesk.eu/glossary/foreground>

⁵ See article 14 of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Grant Agreement, Annex 5, p.4

⁶ See article 14 of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Grant Agreement, Annex 5, p.4

2.2.3 Exploitable results

Exploitation of project's results means the utilisation of results in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned (e.g. in other research activities; or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process; or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities)⁷. Under this scheme, an exploitable result is defined as a project result (expected or achieved) that meets the following two conditions:

- Has commercial/social/academic relevance;
- Can be commercialised/exploited as a standalone result (product, process, service, etc.)⁸.

Therefore, exploitable results can be a combination or part of a foreground result(s). Not all foreground items may meet the above conditions⁹. Furthermore, exploitable results are not necessary market ready; they may require further R&D, engineering and validation before becoming commercially exploitable.

2.2.4 Access rights

Access rights refer to one partner's rights for requesting access to another project partner's background and foreground to implement its activities under the project or to use its own results. Additionally, access rights can be used as long as they are needed for exploiting the project's results. The provisions governing access rights within a collaborative Horizon Europe project follow specific rules pre-defined in the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement. Access rights within SUSTCERT4BIOBASED are presented in the table below:

Table 1. Access Rights

Purpose of access	Access to Background	Access to Results
Project implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Royalty free • Unless otherwise agreed by participants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Royalty free
Exploitation of Own results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subject on individual agreement • Granted under fair and reasonable conditions 	

2.2.5 IP protection

It should be noted that when considering IP protection, IP assets can be protected by several types of IPR, and therefore, the most appropriate protection strategy must be chosen. The selection of the most suitable form of IP protection depends on the nature and specific characteristics of the results under consideration and the objectives of the IP owner.

⁷ <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/support/glossary>

⁸ A patent for licensing is also an exploitable result.

⁹ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/imgs/quick-guide_diss-expl_en.pdf

There are various types of instruments that may be considered for protecting IP. Under the frame of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED, meaningful IP protection instruments that can be used are the following:

- Trade and service marks;
- Patents;
- Utility models;
- Copyrights;
- Trade secrets;
- Confidentiality agreements

Further details about each of the above-mentioned protection instruments are provided in the subsections below.

2.2.5.1 Trade Marks and Service Marks

Trade Marks

A trade mark constitutes an exclusive right over the use of a sign in relation to the goods and services for which it is registered¹⁰. Trade marks consist of signs capable of distinguishing the products (either goods or services) of a trader from those of others. The main function of a trade mark is to identify the commercial origin of a product. This does not mean that it should inform the consumer of the actual person who has manufactured the product or even the one who is trading in it. It is sufficient that consumers can trust in a given enterprise, not necessarily known to them, being responsible for the product sold under the trademark.

Service Marks

In modern trade, consumers are confronted not only with a vast choice of goods of all kinds but also with an increasing variety of services which tend more and more to be offered on a national and international scale. There is therefore a need for signs that enable consumers to distinguish between different services such as insurance companies, car rental firms, airlines, etc. These signs are called service marks and fulfil essentially the same origin-indicating and distinguishing function for services as trademarks do for goods. Since service marks are signs which are very similar in nature to trademarks, the same criteria could be applied. Thus, service mark protection has sometimes been introduced by a very short amendment to the existing trademark law or simply by providing for protection of service marks under of the provisions of the trademark law¹¹.

2.2.5.2 Patents

A patent is an exclusive right granted for the protection of inventions (products or processes) that offers a new technical solution or facilitates a new way of doing something. The patent holder has the exclusive right to prevent third parties from commercially exploiting their invention for a limited period. In return, the patent holder must disclose the invention to the public in the patent application¹².

¹⁰ For the definition of trademark in Europe, see <https://iprhelpdesk.eu/sites/default/files/2018-12/european-ipr-helpdesk-your-guide-to-ip-in-europe.pdf>

¹¹ See WIPO Intellectual Property Handbook 2008: Policy, Law, and Use. Chapter 2: Fields of Intellectual Property Protection, p. 68f.

¹² Definition of patents in the European context retrieved from: <https://iprhelpdesk.eu/sites/default/files/2018-12/european-ipr-helpdesk-your-guide-to-ip-in-europe.pdf>

Patent owner has the right to decide who may or may not use the patented invention throughout the period during which the invention is protected. Additionally, the patent owner may give permission to other parties, or permit them, to use the invention on mutually agreed terms. The owner may also sell the right to the invention to someone, who then becomes the new owner of the patent. Finally, patents are granted only country by country, some regionally (e.g. European), and may also be used in non-patented territories (although in such case they would not enjoy the patent protection). Once a patent expires, the protection ends, and the invention becomes part of the public domain, meaning that owners do not hold exclusive rights any longer. Therefore, it becomes available for commercial exploitation, free of charge, by others¹³.

2.2.5.3 Utility Models

Also referred to as a “petty patent”, a utility model is an exclusive right granted for an invention, which allows its owner to prevent others from commercially using the protected invention, without their authorisation, for a limited period¹⁴. The inclusion of utility models into the intellectual property system in some countries has the primary objective of nurturing the rapid evolution of indigenous innovativeness, particularly in small and medium-sized enterprises and among individuals¹⁵.

2.2.5.3 Copyrights

Copyright (or author’s right) is the term used to describe the economic and moral rights that creators have over their literary, scientific and artistic works. It is important to note that copyright only protects the expression of ideas represented in a physical embodiment, not the ideas themselves, and provided the expression is original¹⁶. There is not an exhaustive list containing the works that can be protected by copyright. However, there are several works usually covered by copyright at an international level¹⁷:

- literary works such as novels, poems, plays, newspaper articles;
- computer programmes, databases;
- films, musical compositions, and choreographies;
- artistic works such as paintings, drawings, etc; and
- advertisements, maps, and technical drawings.

Copyright protection also includes moral rights, including the right to claim authorship of a work, and the right to oppose changes to it that could harm the creator's reputation. The creator - or the owner of the copyright in a work - can enforce rights administratively and in the courts, by inspection of premises for evidence of production or possession of illegally made “pirated” goods related to protecting works. The owner may obtain court orders to stop such activities, as well as seek damages

¹³ See WIPO Intellectual Property Handbook 2008: Policy, Law and Use. Chapter 2: Fields of Intellectual Property Protection, p. 17.

¹⁴ Definition of utility models in the European context retrieved from <https://iprhelppdesk.eu/sites/default/files/2018-12/european-ipr-helpdesk-your-guide-to-ip-in-europe.pdf>

¹⁵ See WIPO Intellectual Property Handbook 2008: Policy, Law and Use. Chapter 2: Fields of Intellectual Property Protection, p. 40.

¹⁶ See WIPO Intellectual Property Handbook 2008: Policy, Law and Use. Chapter 2: Fields of Intellectual Property Protection, p. 40.

¹⁷ Definition of copyrights in the European context retrieved from <https://iprhelppdesk.eu/sites/default/files/2018-12/european-ipr-helpdesk-your-guide-to-ip-in-europe.pdf>

for loss of financial rewards and recognition. Finally, it is important to note that copyright only protects the expression of ideas represented in a physical embodiment, not the ideas themselves, and provided the expression is original¹⁸.

2.2.5.4 Trade Secrets

Any confidential business information that provides a competitive advantage to an enterprise can be considered a trade secret. The type of information that could be protected as a trade secret is therefore highly diverse. It could include know-how, technical knowledge (potentially protectable as a patent), but also business and commercial data such as lists of customers, business plans, recipes or manufacturing processes¹⁹.

2.2.5.5 Confidentiality Agreements

Confidentiality is an extremely important issue for participants in innovation projects, from the setting-up stage to the implementation and exploitation phases. Exchanging valuable information with other partners is generally a necessity that regularly occurs in collaborative initiatives or undertakings. Accordingly, confidentiality issues and measures should be taken into consideration to safely exchange information, facilitate the project development and ensure the non-disclosure of sensitive technology, business or commercially confidential information. Confidentiality agreements provide protection and security to an organisation that is about to share or make available information to another organisation by ensuring that confidential information will be used only for the permitted purposes agreed between the signatories of the agreement and will not be used or revealed to third parties without consent. Therefore, the signature of a confidentiality agreement could be a very important step to keep confidential information secret in order to maintain a competitive edge²⁰.

There are specific criteria to determine a confidentiality agreement as legally enforceable:

- The information must be secret, i.e. not readily accessible to people that normally deal with this kind of information
- It must have commercial value
- The owner must have taken reasonable steps to protect it

3. Approach

Throughout the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project, key IP and exploitation and sustainability management will build on the pillars of identifying a common understanding concerning the background, foreground, ownership (including joint ownership), access and usage rights, dissemination and exploitation during and after the project development. In this respect, the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Exploitation and sustainability plan applies on a comprehensive framework which separates the IP management processes of the project in the following stages:

¹⁸ See WIPO Intellectual Property Handbook 2008: Policy, Law and Use. Chapter 2: Fields of Intellectual Property Protection, p. 40.

¹⁹ Definition of trade secrets in the European context retrieved from <https://iprhelpdesk.eu/sites/default/files/2018-12/european-ipr-helpdesk-your-guide-to-ip-in-europe.pdf>

²⁰ See confidentiality agreements on the WIPO website: https://www.wipo.int/sme/en/documents/disclosing_inf_fulltext.html

1. Grant Agreement preparation stage;
2. Project implementation stage;
3. Post-project stage.

In this respect, the following figure illustrates the IPR management stages, as considered within SUSTCERT4BIOBASED.

Figure 1. The IPR management stages

3.1 Preparation Stage

Both the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement constitute documents which include a description of several issues related to IPR. Their unique provisions represent a reference point for IPR issues within the project partners. Thus, any further advancements regarding IPR actions to put in place by project partners will be facilitated under the underlying provisions.

3.1.1 Grant Agreement

The Grant Agreement constitutes a contract which sets out the key rules and conditions of the project. It is signed between the EC and the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED partners and represents the main contractual basis for SUSTCERT4BIOBASED while its main points and sections which refer to IPR are included in article 16 "Intellectual property rights (IPR) — background and results — access rights and rights of use"²¹. Under this scheme, the management of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED IP is regulated, whereas access rights and obligations related to the background are set. In addition, the Grant Agreement defines issues concerning the ownership and protection of the project's generated results, as well as their exploitation and dissemination outcomes. Lastly, the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED GA defines transferability and access rights to results.

3.1.2 Consortium Agreement

The Consortium Agreement constitutes a contract among the partners of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED consortium which aims to define rights and obligations during the

²¹ In particular, see Article 16 of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Grant Agreement

partnership for the purposes of carrying out the project's foreseen actions and activities²². The Consortium Agreement minimises the probability of later disputes as it provides rules and responsibilities during the project and defines the access rights to be granted to the partners concerning the project. In addition, it outlines rights and responsibilities among the consortium members concerning issues of the IP.

The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Consortium Agreement main points and sections referring to IPR are included in:

- **Section 8 “Results”**, that sets out provisions on ownership and joint ownership of results, as well as on their transfer and dissemination.
- **Section 9 “Access Rights”**, which clarifies the access rights governing principles along with the access rights for the exploitation and dissemination purposes.
- **Attachment 1 “Background included”** that presents the initial list of usable background.

3.2 Implementation Stage

During the implementation stage of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED, IP handling procedures are foreseen to be applied among the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED partners to organise the results/assets management of the project. As the project continues, the focus will be on foreground identification, assets' ownership, access rights, and protection, as well as on the exploitation and commercialisation of the project's results. The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED IPR management emphasises on establishing robust handling procedures of the IPR issues that are of strategic importance to the project in order to facilitate the exploitation of its results.

Therefore, partners should focus on two different points:

- Providing access rights to their knowledge for other partners to carry out their work on the project.
- Establishing early asset identification procedures to protect, disseminate and exploit the project's assets.

In this respect, key IP related issues in the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED implementation phase include:

3.2.1 *Background identification*

During the first stages of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED is vital to identify the relevant knowledge, know-how, and data of partners, complementary to those outlined in the Consortium Agreement, elements that constitute the background of the project. Under this framework, the underlying background could be attached to the generated assets of the project, which, eventually, will help the determination of access rights, ownership issues and IPR.

3.2.2 *Foreground identification*

A core process of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED IP management is the project assets' identification to create a concrete mapping of the projects' assets and enhance the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED IP portfolio. Therefore, all IP valuable assets within the project must be identified, listed, named, described and analysed in a systematic way.

²² See IPR helpdesk for the definition of Consortium Agreement.

3.2.3 Results' ownership

Partners have been asked (through the SUSTCER4BIOBASED IPR Matrix) to elaborate further on the provisions of the Consortium Agreement regarding the results' ownership. Special attention will be paid on handling joint ownership issues.

3.2.4 Protection of results

Effective exploitation of the innovative concepts and assets developed under the frame of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED depends on the protection of the project's results. In particular, the project's results must adequately be protected if²³:

- The project's results can reasonably be expected to be commercially exploited and;
- Protecting them is possible, reasonable and justified (given the circumstances).

On this note, when considering IP protection, SUSTCERT4BIOBASED partners must consider their own interests along with the interests of the consortium. Project partners should safeguard the identified exploitable SUSTCERT4BIOBASED results with adequate protection schemes, which will offer adequate protection period within a suitable geographical territory. The geographical territory should be agreed by the parties in advance, based on where the IP will be used. By default, Europe is considered to be the suitable territory in which the identified exploitable SUSTCERT4BIOBASED results will be safeguarded, but it remains at the discretion of the interested parties to collectively reach an agreement regarding this matter.

The table that follows, illustrates an indicative list of different protection instruments. The ones most applicable to the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project are highlighted in Green, as considering the CSA nature of the project, it is not expected to employ all the instruments in the list. Furthermore, additional protection instruments can be used when deemed suitable as the project activities progress.

Table 2. List of different protection instruments (the most applicable to SUSTCERT4BIOBASED assets can be found highlighted in Green).

Subject Matter	Patent	Utility	Copyright	Trademark	Confidential Information
Invention	X	X			X
Software	X ²⁴	X	X		X
Scientific Article			X		
Technology Design			X	X	
Name of Technology				X	

²³ See <https://cms.eurice.eu/storage/uploads/news/files/ip-management-in-collab-horizon-projects.pdf>

²⁴ Software patentability is still a debated issue given its exclusion as subject matter as by Article 52(2)(c) and (3) of the European Patent Convention (EPC). Source: IPR Helpdesk.

Know How	X	X			X
Website			X	X	X

IP protection constitutes a tool to create value through the licensing, sale or commercialisation of IP in the form of products and services. IP utilisation is vital for a prospective commercial or industrial exploitation as it could contribute to support the branding of products and services both to customers and investors. It should be noted that the IP protection of an asset is not always mandatory.

3.2.5 *Exploitation of results*

The identified exploitable results and assets of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED will be effectively exploited for commercial or any other relevant use as foreseen during the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project. In particular, the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED consortium will seek exploitation opportunities of the project's results in:

- i) further research activities,
- ii) developing, creating or marketing a product or process,
- iii) creating and providing a service,
- iv) using them in standardisation activities.

3.2.6 *Dissemination of results*

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED partners are set to select the appropriate means for the dissemination of the project's results (e.g. scientific publications, publication on web sites, conferences, open access, etc.), based on the conditions set forth in the CA²⁵ and in other specific confidentiality agreements. All partners should be aware that they should first ensure the protection of a project's exploitable result and then proceed to dissemination actions of the underlying result.

3.3 Post project Stage

At the project's formal conclusion in M36, the final version of D6.8 SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Exploitation and Sustainability Plan – updated will be submitted. It will include the final outline of the use which the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED consortium intends to make its exploitable foreground (including its final description and sector of application) and the related plans and time frame for their exploitation.

D6.8 will describe further the activities that will be developed to deploy the dissemination and exploitation of the project's achievements and the activities that aim to ensure the sustainability of the project's results. Additionally, D6.8 will include the final findings regarding IP issues and the final update of the IPR Matrix presenting in detail the applied and registered intellectual property rights.

The aforementioned deliverable will present the final advanced strategy for the exploitation and management of IPR and the sustainability after the project ends, including also the concrete chosen commercialisation streams.

²⁵ See Section 8.4 of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Consortium Agreement.

3.4 Role of the Exploitation Manager

The Exploitation Manager (EM) is responsible for defining the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Exploitation and sustainability Plan. The tasks include preparing the respective reports and ensuring that innovative ideas which come up during the project will be thoroughly examined and assessed for potential exploitation, while at the same time all BG and FG IP of the project is properly managed. To this end, the Exploitation Manager will be in close communication with the Project Coordinator and the Steering Committee to ensure the optimal management of all IP assets.

The Exploitation Manager and the Project Coordinator will be responsible for the organisation and management issues of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED IPR strategy implementation. With that said, it could be considered as a good practice for a partner to inform and consult the EM and the PC accordingly before deciding whether to protect the results stemming from its underlying activities or not – particularly if the partner is considering a potential joint IP scheme.

Lastly, the Exploitation manager has also a mediation role in case of IP conflicts (see Section 3.6), monitors project activities and feeds the development of the subsequent versions of this report in the context of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED.

3.5 Knowledge Management of the project

The management of the IP constitutes an integral part of the overall SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project management structure and thus it is important to establish a permanent IP monitoring during the project. In this respect, an efficient IPR management methodology should define, from the early stages of the project, the procedures under which newly generated/identified results will be handled during the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's lifecycle.

Efficient management of IP in SUSTCERT4BIOBASED will be achieved through adopting a process able to identify IP results as well as to determine their adequate handling and protection. In this respect, it is essential to establish mechanisms that will guarantee that IP information is reliable and timely captured. In case WP Leaders identify a new asset that will be generated under their respective WP activities, the Exploitation Manager should be informed accordingly.

The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Exploitation Manager and the PC, together with the partners producing the newly identified asset, constitute the parties that will handle the screening and the managing of any newly identified assets and their corresponding IP issues. The Exploitation Manager will direct the consortium partners to establish the most adequate and efficient IPR strategy based on the nature of the newly identified asset and the purposes of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED consortium.

To facilitate this process, the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Exploitation and Sustainability plan foresees to create and update a living IPR Matrix to be revised and extended with new pieces of assets and project results (FG).

3.6 IP Conflicts

In order to proactively avoid IP conflicts, project partners will be well-informed about IP rules and guided through the exploitation process not only via the IPR Matrix but also through the help of the Exploitation Manager. In this respect, project partners will identify their IPR assets, formulate their ownership and exploitation claims and if deemed necessary, transfer any relevant results to

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's exploitable results according to the principle rights and obligations defined in the CA of the project²⁶.

The Exploitation Manager will provide assistance for the following indicative (and not exclusive) issues:

- Is there a possible misunderstanding about the definition of the exploitable result and therefore of the object of claims?
- Are there exploitation claims that should be further specified so that the partners can check the compatibility of their claims?
- Are the foreseen exploitation claims compatible with the ownership claims of the partners (related issue of access rights)?
- Are there any confidentiality issues e.g. on new knowledge of strategic importance for a partner and consequently the need for a confidential agreement?
- Are there any possible IP conflicts between the partners, both related to ownership and the related need for access rights and to exploitation claims?

In case of IP conflict, the Exploitation Manager will encourage conflicting parties to get in contact and pro-actively find solutions and sign written agreements whenever necessary. In case no agreement is achieved, an internal mediation process will be kicked off following the provisions of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's CA. In case the IP issues remain unresolved after this first mediation procedure, a further mediation process in accordance with the WIPO Mediation Rules will be applied²⁷.

²⁶ See Section 8 of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Consortium Agreement.

²⁷ See Section 11.8 of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Consortium Agreement.

4. IPR Matrix methodology

The IPR Matrix will be used in the framework of the project to define the main IPR issues related to the Exploitation and sustainability strategy. This approach will facilitate the consortium partners to identify the background, foreground, and exploitable results. In addition, the IP protection measures, and the necessary agreements will be defined to ensure the successful exploitation of the project outcomes even after the completion of the project.

The IPR methodology follows 4 interconnected steps:

1. **Identification of the Background IP** and definition of the access rights of the consortium partners
2. Preliminary **identification of the foreground IP** that will be produced in the framework of the project's activities.
3. Initial **identification of the exploitable assets/results** that will be produced in the framework of the project and the interest for their commercialisation.
4. **Definition of the IPR protection** of the identified exploitable assets/results that can be potentially commercially exploited by the consortium partners.

At this early stage of the project, the objective of the Exploitation and Sustainability Plan of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED is to define the main assets on the one hand and identify, to the extent possible, the FG and BG IPs of the project along with their corresponding access rights on the other hand. During the later stages of the project's implementation, the IPR methodology will be devised accordingly, in order to capture and integrate the evolvement of the identified results and IPR approach of the project. In particular, the identification of exploitable assets would yield the need to establish an ownership regime among project partners for each one of the exploitable results. In addition, rules and conditions to get access to exploitable results need also to be considered. Finally, validation of the IPR needs to be meticulously employed. Under this framework, the structure of the IPR Matrix that will be used throughout the duration of the project is summarised in the following table.

Table 3. Structure of the IPR Matrix

Background (BG)	Foreground (FG)	Exploitable results (ER)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ BG# ○ Partner's Background ○ Contributing Partner ○ Short Description of BG ○ Type of Protection ○ How will it be utilised within SUSTCERT4BIOBASED? ○ Conditions to Use within SUSTCERT4BIOBASED 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ FG# ○ Project Outcome /Achievement/Result ○ Related WP ○ Contributing Partners ○ Short Description of FG ○ Related BG# (BG owner) ○ Type of Protection ○ Conditions to Use within SUSTCERT4BIOBASED 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ ER# ○ Exploitable result ○ Main partner ○ Further contributing partner(s) ○ Related FG# ○ Related project task/deliverable (if applicable)

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Conditions to use outside SUSTCERT4BIOBASED ○ Interest in further exploitation through SUSTCERT4BIOBASED results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Interest in Further Commercialisation of Project Results ○ Conditions to Use after the end of the Project 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Related BG# (BG owner) ○ Proposition for the ER- owner ○ Short description of the ER ○ Relevance for IP Protection
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4.1 Identification of Background IP

During the first stage of the IPR Matrix the Background that will be used during the implementation of the project were identified.

Table 4. IPR Matrix Background

#	Relevant Background	Contributing Partner	Background Number	Short Description of BG	Type of Protection	How will it be utilised within SUSTCERT4BIOBASED?	Conditions to Use within SUSTCERT4BIOBASED	outside SUSTCERT4BIOBASED	through SUSTCERT4BIOBASED results

Multiple information regarding the Background IP is recorded in the respective template. In the second column of the table a short name of the Background is given. Then, the responsible partner is mentioned, and a number is assigned related to the Work package and the number of assets. In the 5th column of the table a short more detailed description regarding the BG is offered. Furthermore, the partners define the Type of protection in terms of patents, utility models, copyrights, trade and service marks, trade secrets, creative commons licenses, confidentiality agreements, among others. In column 7, the partners define how this BG will be used in the framework of the project, and then in columns 8 and 9 describe the conditions under which the consortium partners and the stakeholders outside the consortium respectively can use the BG. Finally, the partners should state their interest for further exploitation of the BG in the framework of the project through the produced results.

The background IP was registered by the project partners by M6, as perceived at that stage of the project. The results are presented in the next chapter.

4.2 Identification of Foreground IP

In the second stage of the IPR Matrix the partners have identified the Foreground that will be produced during the project’s activities.

Table 5. IPR Matrix Foreground

Work Package	PR number	Project Outcome /Achievement/ Result	Specific Project Result	Main Contributing Partner	Further Contributing Partner(s)	Related Background Number	Short Description of FG	Foreground Number	Type of Protection	Conditions to Use within SUSTCERT4BIOBASED	Interest in Further Commercialisation of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Results	Conditions to Use after the end of the Project

The above template is used by the consortium partners to identify the foreground IP. In the first four columns the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project achievements are listed along with the respective WP. Then, the main contributing partner is mentioned. Usually, if an FG comes as a direct result of a Task, then the main partner is the Task leader. In addition, the rest of the contributing partners are also mentioned. Similarly, the contributing partners are usually the partners contributing to the Task that the FG emerges from. In the 7th column the number of the related Background IP is mentioned while in column 8 is given a short description of the FG. Furthermore, a Foreground number is assigned to the respective FG. Similarly, to the background identification template, the partners also define the type of protection, the conditions under which the FG can be used by the consortium partners and the interest for the commercialisation through the project results. Finally, in the last column, the conditions (e.g., free to use, license fee, etc.) to use after the end of the project shall be indicated by the project partners.

The identified Foreground IP up until M6 can be found in the respective chapter.

4.3 Identification of exploitable results

In the third stage and based on the identified FG the consortium partners will define the exploitable results and the IPR management procedures:

- i) Protection
- ii) Definition of access rights
- iii) Exploitation pathways

The main aim of this third stage of the IPR Matrix where the exploitable results and the main contributors will be defined will be:

- to identify IP ownership and exploitation claims, as well as pro-actively indicate possible conflicts for each exploitable result; and
- to support decisions on issues pertaining to IP protection, in order to timely make the needed steps in this regard, including any potential IP agreements (e.g., for joint ownership, providing access rights or even an NDA for confidentiality)

The next table will be used throughout the whole duration of the project in order to deploy the third stage of the IPR Matrix and identify the exploitable results.

Table 6. IPR Matrix Exploitable Results

ER number	Exploitable Result (ER)	Short Description	Main Partner(s)	Contributing Partners	FG number (related)	BG number (related)	Proposition for ER - Owner (if any)	Relevance for IP protection (if any)	M - Making them and selling them	U - Using them	L - Licence them	S - Providing as a Service	O - Others	Most promising path	Further Comments (Please insert any further comments that you might have)

In the first three columns, the number, a short name and a brief description of the exploitable results will be mentioned. In the next two columns the main responsible partner and the rest contributing partners will be listed. In column 6th and 7th, the number of the related FG and BG will be indicated. In addition, in the next column the proposed owner of the exploitable result will be defined, while in column 9 the relevance for IP protection will be indicated by the responsible partner. The next 5 columns indicate the 5 different categories of the exploitation claims.

- **M:** Making a product and selling it.
- **U:** Using the project result internally for further development, for instance:
 - to develop something else for sale; or
 - for R&D departments (public or private) to use the results in new research projects.

- **L:** Licensing the project result to third parties.
- **S:** Providing a Service, such as consultancy, etc.
- **O:** Others

The partner responsible for the exploitable results with the support of the contributing partners, the coordinator and the exploitation manager shall choose which exploitation claims best fit the ER. In the final column the most promising exploitation claim shall be indicated.

5. Overview of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED assets, Background and Foreground IP

5.1 Identified Assets of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED

The table below presents the identified assets and their short description as were defined by the consortium partners during these early stages of the project.

Table 7. Identified assets of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED

Asset	Description
<i>SUSTCERT4BIOBASED monitoring framework</i>	A monitoring system to assess existing schemes and labels for biological resources and biobased materials and products. The system will assess the coverage of the list of the minimum requirements and provide information on the strengths and weaknesses
<i>SUSTCERT4BIOBASED costs benefit assessment method</i>	Implementation of the cost benefit analysis (CBA) to certification schemes. The method is often applied in policy assessments and currently few examples exist regarding its application to certification schemes. The method will be tailored to the biobased industry and will be applied to three biobased value chains.
<i>SUSTCERT4BIOBASED costs benefit assessment template</i>	Development of a data collection template considering the direct and indirect economic, environmental, and social aspects. This template will be filled with the costs and benefits associated with the adoption of best-in-class certification schemes and labels in three biobased value chains and will gather data that will be later be used in the cost benefit analysis.
<i>Catalogue of sustainability certification schemes and labels relevant for biobased systems</i>	A catalogue including sustainability certification schemes classified according to the biological feedstock and biobased product. Fact sheets for each reviewed scheme/label will be also prepared.
<i>SUSTCER4BIOBASED best practices and recommendations for the adoption of effective and robust sustainability schemes and labels</i>	Thematic briefs tailored to each target group. The briefs will be created by synthesising the findings and will include recommendations for the adoption of sustainability schemes and labels.
<i>Mapping of biobased value chains and selection methodology</i>	The biobased value chains will be identified and evaluated based on a set of criteria. A multicriteria methodology based on the Analytical Hierarchical Process (AHP) approach will be applied to generate local and global weighting for the specific

	criteria. The assessment of the results following the AHP method will provide a pre-selection of the most representative value chains.
<i>Data and figures on volumes of biological resources and biobased products in global trade flows</i>	Data on volumes of biological resources and biobased products in global trade flows acquired based on existing and consolidated market databases, previous projects, publicly available sources, dedicated surveys, and interviews with industrial stakeholders and scheme and label owners
<i>Research publications – open access</i>	Scientific papers published or co-published by the consortium partners based on the project’s results
<i>Project deliverables</i>	Dissemination material and reports demonstrating key project outputs with a potential interest of exploitation.
<i>SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Web portal</i>	The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED portal will be used to communicate and diffuse the project’s results and outcomes to the relevant stakeholders

5.2 Background IP

The project partners preliminary identified the background IP to be used to achieve the objectives of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED. The Background IP is presented in the table below:

Table 8. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Identified IP BG

#	Relevant BG	Contributing Partner	BG Number	Short Description of BG	Type of Protection	How will it be utilised within SUSTCERT4BIOBASED?	Conditions to Use within SUSTCERT4BIOBASED	Conditions to use outside SUSTCERT4BIOBASED	Interest in further exploitation through SUSTCERT4BIOBASED results
1	Winery sustainability tool	CIRCE	BG 1.1	In the project SMART MANAGING SUSTAINABLE WINE [PDR FEADER 2014-2020 N° 210190002) CIRCE has developed a tool to assess sustainability in the winery industry.	Copyright	This platform allows to monitor economic, technical and environmental KPIs specified for the wine sector, and its conclusions can be used to have an initial background for the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project	Right for using the Background within the project, limited to the specific activities in relation to the tool.	This Background will not be used for other uses than the project purposes unless otherwise agreed under fair and reasonable conditions.	yes

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2	Know-how on environmental sustainability criteria	WFBR	BG 1.2	Review of environmental criteria within standards and certification schemes as part of Biobased plastic project (under Framework Contract ENV/F1/FRA/2019/00 01)	Intangible asset / Experience	This knowledge will be utilised in T1.2 in compilation of sustainability principles and criteria	Right for using the Background within the project, limited to the specific activities in relation with this knowledge	This Background will not be used for other uses than the project purposes, unless otherwise agreed under fair and reasonable conditions.	yes
3	Know-how on range of biological resources	WFBR	BG1.3	Classification system developed as part of Biorefinery outlook project as well as other projects working with a range of biomass feedstocks	Intangible asset / Experience	This knowledge will be utilised in T1.1 in developing the classification of biological resources	Right for using the Background within the project, limited to the specific activities in relation with the tool.	This Background will not be used for other uses than the project purposes, unless otherwise agreed under fair and reasonable conditions.	yes
4	Overview of existing sustainability certification frameworks	ECOS	BG1.4	Deliverable D1.1 Report on identified environmental, social and economic criteria/indicators/requirements and related "Gap Analysis"	copyright	This information will be utilised in T1.3 in identifying relevant sustainability certification schemes/labels for biobased systems	Right for using the Background within the project, limited to the specific activities in relation with this knowledge	This Background will not be used for other uses than the project purposes, unless otherwise agreed under fair and reasonable conditions.	yes

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5	Know-how on governance of certification schemes	WFBR + CU	BG1.5	Expert knowledge related to the governance aspects of certification schemes	Intangible asset / Experience	This knowledge will be utilised in T1.2 in compilation of governance principles	Right for using the Background within the project, limited to the specific activities in relation with this knowledge	This Background will not be used for other uses than the project purposes, unless otherwise agreed under fair and reasonable conditions.	yes
6	Biobased chemicals in EU economic classifications	WECR	BG1.6	Database on C20 category chemicals and the entries that refer to biobased chemicals - from BioMonitor project	Copyright	This knowledge will be utilised in T1.1 in developing classification of biobased chemicals	Right for using the Background within the project, limited to aggregated chemical application in relation with this knowledge	This Background will not be used for other uses than the project purposes, unless otherwise agreed under fair and reasonable conditions.	yes
7	Biobased shares and biological feedstock conversion factors in C20 products	WECR	BG1.7	Database on C20 category chemicals and the entries that refer to biobased chemicals - from BioMonitor project	Copyright	This knowledge will be utilised in T1.1 in developing classification of biobased chemicals	Right for using the Background within the project, limited to aggregated chemical application in relation with this knowledge	This Background will not be used for other uses than the project purposes, unless otherwise agreed under fair and reasonable conditions.	yes

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8	Know-how on calculator or platform	CIRCE	BG 2.1	Expertise on calculator platform based on algorithms and analytical hierarchy process methodology.	Intangible asset / Experience / Protection: TBD	The expertise will be valuable to address relevant tasks having some assumptions and being faster in its advance	Right for using the Background within the project, limited to the specific activities in relation with this knowledge.	This Background will not be used for other uses than the project purposes, unless otherwise agreed under fair and reasonable conditions.	yes
9	Tool to catalogue valorisation solutions	CIRCE	BG 2.2	In the project WAYSTUP! CIRCE has developed a multi criterium prioritisation tool to create a catalogue of valorisation solutions.	n/a (TBD)	The expertise will be valuable to address relevant tasks having some assumptions and being faster in its advance. This experience on previous tool will ease and make faster the selection of other licenses to work in the project. Connected to BG2.1	Right for using the Background within the project, limited to the specific activities in relation with the tool.	This Background will not be used for other uses than the project purposes, unless otherwise agreed under fair and reasonable conditions.	yes
10	Experience in working with (large) data basis (PRODCOM, COMEXT)	WECR	BG2.3	In BioMonitor project collected data on trade of bio-based chemical applications at MS level.	Intangible asset / Experience	This knowledge will be utilised in T2.2 in getting trade volumes of biobased chemical applications	Right for using the Background within the project, limited to aggregated chemical application in relation with this knowledge	This Background will not be used for other uses than the project purposes, unless otherwise agreed under fair and reasonable conditions.	yes

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11	Experience in using economic methods for analysing	WECR	BG2.4	Expertise used in BioMonitor; regular market outlook studies for DG-AGRI	Intangible asset / Experience	This knowledge will be utilised in T2.4 in using gravity methods to understand effects of certification on trade	Right for using the Background within the project, limited to the specific activities in relation with this knowledge	This Background will not be used for other uses than the project purposes, unless otherwise agreed under fair and reasonable conditions.	yes
12	Sustainability standard comparison tool	WFBR	BG 3.1	A tool developed as part of a study comparing sustainability issues based on urgency	Copyright	This study will be used for inspiration in developing the monitoring system in WP3	Right for using the Background within the project, limited to the specific activities in relation with this knowledge	This Background will not be used for other uses than the project purposes, unless otherwise agreed under fair and reasonable conditions.	yes
13	Optimisation of furnaces tool	CIRCE	BG 3.2	Tool developed by CIRCE under VULKANO project (H2020, GA N° 723803) focused on the optimisation of furnaces used in three energy intensive industrial sectors (aluminum, steel and ceramic furnaces).	Not protected	This platform allows to monitor different performance KPIs of baselines and innovations (economic, technical and environmental).	Right for using the Background within the project, limited to the specific activities in relation with the tool.	This Background will not be used for other uses than the project purposes, unless otherwise agreed under fair and reasonable conditions.	yes

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14	Blueprint of sustainability certification schemes for bio-based products	ECOS	BG 3.3	Deliverable D8.2 of sustainability certification schemes for bio-based products, which includes the sustainability assessment tool (SAT) and the sustainability certification tools (SCT)	copyright	This information will be used as input in T3.2 when developing the monitoring system	Right for using the Background within the project, limited to the specific activities in relation with this knowledge	This Background will not be used for other uses than the project purposes, unless otherwise agreed under fair and reasonable conditions.	yes
15	Know-how on Cost-benefit Analysis	WECR	BG 4.1	Expertise on calculating costs benefits including internalisation of externalities	Intangible asset / Experience	The expertise will be valuable to address the Task 4.5 Quantification of costs and benefits of data from Task 4.4	Right for using the Background within the project, limited to the specific activities in relation with this knowledge	The background is not confidential and can be shared with externals	yes

16	Knowledge of the policy framework related to bioeconomy	ECOS	BG5.1	Deliverable 9.3 Proposal for a co-regulation framework for the use of sustainability certification schemes in the production of bio-based products	copyright	This document provides background on how the relationship between policies and private VSS should operate and therefore will be used as background when developing tailored policy recommendations	Right for using the Background within the project, limited to the specific activities in relation with this knowledge	This Background will not be used for other uses than the project purposes, unless otherwise agreed under fair and reasonable conditions.	yes
17	Bioeconomy Strategy Accelerator Toolkit	CIRCE	BG5.2	In the context of the H2020 Power4Bio project, with GA n° 818351, BSAT (Bioeconomy Strategy Accelerator Toolkit) was created.	Open Access	This is an online platform acting as a repository to provide information to guide decisions-makers and stakeholders. This information helps policy makers to develop their regional bioeconomy strategy. The toolkit contributes to identifying specific regional assets, gaps, weaknesses. Also, it provides tips on how to develop or strengthen its own regional bioeconomy strategy. Available in http://bioeconomy-strategy-toolkit.eu/	Rights for using the Background within the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project.	This Background is available in open access for its exploitation in http://bioeconomy-strategy-toolkit.eu/	yes

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18	Know how on website content development and management	WHITE	BG6.1	Previous experience on developing project's website and day - to day management	Intangible asset / Experience	This knowledge will be used in order to develop the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED website	free to use	This Background will not be used for other uses than the project purposes	no
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5.3 Foreground IP

A preliminary identification of the Foreground IP took place during the initial stages of the project and can be found in the table below. Additional updates or modifications are expected in the updated version of the Exploitation and Sustainability Plan, which will correspond to the progress of the project and the produced results and knowhow.

Table 9. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Identified IP FG

WP	#	Project Outcome /Achievement/ Result	Specific Project Result	Main Contributing Partner	Further Contributing Partner(s)	Related BG Number	Short Description of FG	FG Number	Type of Protection	Conditions to Use within SUSTCERT4BIOBASED	Interest in Further Commercialisation of project's Results	Conditions to Use after the end of the Project
WP1	PR 1.1	Classification of biobased products	Identification of biological resources and biobased products and their classification	CIRCE	WR, CU	BG1.3, BG 1.6	Identification and classification of the wide range of biological resources and biobased products that are available in the EU economy.	FG 1.1	Copyright	Right for using the Background within the project, limited to the specific activities in relation with the task	yes	Specific agreement / contract to be studied
	PR 1.2	Review and analysis of schemes and labels	Methodology for reviewing schemes/labels	WR	ECOS	No BG related to this asset	Methodology developed for reviewing schemes/labels related to their coverage of sustainability and governance aspects	FG 1.2	Copyright	Free to use	no	TBD

	PR 1.3		Identification and reviewing of existing sustainability certification schemes and labels relevant to biobased value chains	WR	CIRCE, CU	No BG related to this asset	The sustainability schemes and labels relevant to the biobased products defined in the framework of the project will be further identified and will be analysed by using the developed methodology.	FG 1.3	TBD	Free to use	no	TBD
	PR 1.4		Compilation of sustainability principles and criteria	WFBR	CIRCE, CU	BG1.2, BG1.5	Compilation of sustainability principles and criteria from review of relevant legislation, standards, schemes and studies	FG 1.4	Copyright	Free to use	no	TBD
	PR 1.5		Catalogue of sustainability certification schemes and labels	WFBR	CIRCE, CU	BG1.4	Catalogue of the reviewed certification schemes/labels composed of factsheets providing overview of each	FG1.5	Copyright	Free to use	no	TBD

	PR 1.6	Analysis of synergies and trade-offs	A qualitative analysis identifying the trade-offs and synergies within the sustainability dimensions	CIRCE	WR,CU, ECOS	No BG related to this asset	Scheme owners and industry experience will be collected through interviews and their relationships will be mapped. In addition data will showcase the trade-offs between the resources and products	FG1.6	TBD	Right for using the Background within the project, limited to the specific activities in relation with the task	yes	Specific agreement / contract to be studied
WP2	PR 2.1	Identify biobased value chains with higher potential for biobased certificates / labels	A multicriteria methodology in order to identify the most representative biobased value chains	CIRCE	WR,CU	No BG related to this asset	Report on identified most representative biobased value chains	FG 2.1	Copyright	Right for using the Background within the project, limited to the specific activities in relation with the task	yes	Specific agreement / contract to be studied
	PR 2.2	Quantification of global trade flows of biobased value chains	Database of trade volumes for biological resources and biobased products	WECR	CIRCE, CU	BG2.3	Database with trade volumes for selected value chains in	FG 2.2	Copyright	Right for using the Background within the project, limited to the specific activities in relation with the task; restricted use in case of stakeholder details	no	TBD

	PR 2.3	Build knowledge on analysing effects of certification on EU trade of biobased value chains	Knowledge based on literature review, interviews and surveys with scheme owners and biobased value chain actors and traders	WECR	CIRCE	BG2.4	Report on analysed effects of certification on EU trade of biobased value chains	FG 2.3	Copyright	Free to use	no	TBD
WP3	PR 3.1	Monitoring system	Identifying existing monitoring approaches	ECOS	WR,CU	BG 3.1, 3.2	Includes review of SAI Platform's FSA Tool, GSSI's Global Benchmark Tool, WWF's CAT	FG 3.1	Copyright	Free to use	no	TBD
	PR 3.2		Developing a new monitoring system	ECOS	WR,CU	BG 3.1, 3.2, 3.3	Internal report describing the methodology of the monitoring system to assess the completeness, effectiveness, and robustness of existing voluntary sustainability instruments.	FG 3.2	Copyright	Free to use	yes	TBD

	PR 3.3	Testing the developed monitoring system	Assessing existing schemes and labels	WFBR	CIRCE, ECOS	BG 3.2	Results from the testing of the developed monitoring system on the selected schemes/labels. Identification of strengths/weaknesses based on these results.	FG 3.3	Copyright	Free to use	no	TBD
	PR 3.4		Carrying out pilot audits	CU	CIRCE, ECOS	No BG related to this asset	Results from testing the developed monitoring system by carrying out a pilot testing and audit on a supply chain.	FG3.4	TBD	Free to use	no	TBD
WP4	PR 4.1	Cost feasibility assessment and	Executing a Cost Benefit Analysis (CBA)	WR	CU	BG 4.1	Review of methodologies for cost benefit analysis and internalising externalities for sustainability certification	FG 4.1	Copyright	Free to use	no	TBD
	PR 4.2		Data Collection Template	CU	WR	BG 4.2, BG 1.5	Templates to collect data from three	FG 4.2	Copyright	Free to use	no	TBD

							selected value chains					
	PR 4.3		Collection of data for the selected biobased value chains	CU	WR	BG 4.2, BG 1.5	Dataset from filling up the template for the 3 selected biobased value chains	FG 4.3	Copyright	Restricted use with NDA	no	TBD
WP5	PR 5.1	Synthesis of results and recommendations	Recommendations to policy makers	ECOS	WR,CU	BG 5.1	Two policy briefs targeting various institutions and policy makers, at international, European, and national levels	FG 5.1	Free to use	Free to use	yes	Free to use
	PR 5.2		Recommendations to standards writers, scheme owners and certification bodies	ECOS	WR,CU	BG 5.1	Thematic briefs laying down recommendations to scheme/label owners	FG 5.2	Free to use	Free to use	yes	Free to use
	PR 5.3		Recommendations to industrial biobased value chain actors	CIRCE	WR,CU	BG 5.1	Thematic briefs to industrial biobased value chain actors	FG 5.3	Free to use	Free to use	yes	Free to use
	PR 5.4		Recommendations to regional	CIRCE	ECOS,CU	BG 5.1	Thematic briefs to regional	FG 5.4	Free to use	Free to use	yes	Free to use

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			bioeconomy actors				bioeconomy actors					
WP6	PR 6.1	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED website	Development and management of the project's website	WHITE	All	BG6.1	Website to present and promote the project and its results.	FG6.1	Creative Commons License	Free to use	no	Free to use
	RP 6.2	Creating a community related to the project and its results	Development of the Network of Interest	WHITE	All	No BG related to this asset	Engaging at least 50 relevant stakeholders and support the knowledge exchange around the sector	FG6.2	Free to use	Free to use	no	free to use
	PR 6.3	Contacts with relevant actors	Connection with industry interested in biobased certification to present our results	CIRCE	All	No BG related to this asset	Identifying lists of relevant industry stakeholders which are interested in the project's results	FG 6.3	Confidentiality agreements	Right for using the Background within the project, limited to the specific activities in relation with the task	yes	Specific agreement / contract to be studied

6. Conclusions

This initial version of the report on Exploitation and Sustainability Plan has presented the main elements of the IPR approach, the methodology employed in this respect as well as provided an overview of the project's assets, background and foreground IP. To facilitate the identification and the management of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's assets, a dedicated tool has been elaborated under the supervision of the Exploitation Manager, the IPR Matrix.

The final version of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Exploitation and Sustainability Plan report will be updated in M36 of the project, depicting the latest status in terms of project results' identification, type of protection, ownership and access rights definition, with the support of all partners. The final version of the report will provide more details on the exploitable assets of the project and the framework of their exploitation, to support the sustainability and continuation of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's outcomes.

The Exploitation Manager is responsible for keeping the Exploitation and Sustainability Plan updated. The EM will monitor the project's activities as they evolve, will timely capture innovation opportunities that may go unnoticed, as well as will identify any potential conflicts of interest and facilitate their resolution before the end of the project. Thus, a proactive smooth post-project exploitation of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED results will be fostered.

About SUSTCERT4BIOBASED

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED is an EU funded (Horizon Europe) project aiming at defining and promoting the adoption of effective and robust sustainability certification schemes and business-to-business labels for industrial biobased systems to support tracing the sustainability (environmental, social, economic) of biobased products along the value chains and trades within the EU and globally for responsible production and consumption. This objective is realised by the development of a monitoring system, mapping of the current situation in global trade flows of biological resources and biobased products, and feasibility assessment from the adoption of certification schemes and labels considering actual economic as well as internalised environmental and social costs and benefits. The results of the project are leveraged to provide recommendations to four key target groups: policy makers, sustainability system community, industrial biobased value chain actors, and regional bioeconomy stakeholders. These ambitions are addressed by a strong, well-balanced and multi-disciplinary consortium comprised of 5 complementary partners. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED thereby supports the development of harmonised system requirements, continuous improvement of sustainability certification schemes and labels and contributes towards establishing a circular, climate-neutral and sustainable biobased industry.

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